

Correction

Correction: Gaglio et al. Performances of Different Metabolic *Lactobacillus* Groups during the Fermentation of Pizza Doughs Processed from Semolina. *Fermentation* 2018, 4, 61

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The authors wish to make the following corrections to this paper [1]:

In the abstract section, there are some errors. We mistakenly indicated that *Lactobacillus sanfranciscensis*, *Lactobacillus brevis*, and *Lactobacillus rossiae* are part of the facultative homofermentative group and *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus graminis*, and *Lactobacillus curvatus* are part of the obligate heterofermentative group (lines 3–4 in the abstract), but the opposite is true. *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus graminis*, *Lactobacillus curvatus* are facultative, and *Lactobacillus sanfranciscensis*, *Lactobacillus brevis*, and *Lactobacillus rossiae* are obligate.

The correct version is as follows:

The main hypothesis of this work is that facultative and obligate heterofermentative *Lactobacillus* species can differently impact the final characteristics of pizza. The objective was to evaluate separately the behaviors of the obligate heterofermentative species (OHS), such as *Lactobacillus sanfranciscensis*, *Lactobacillus brevis*, and *Lactobacillus rossiae*, and the facultative heterofermentative species (FHS), including *Lactobacillus plantarum*, and *Lactobacillus curvatus*, in the sourdoughs to be used for pizza production. The production of the experimental pizzas was carried out with semolina (*Triticum turgidum* L. ssp. *durum*). The acidification process—which was followed by pH, total titratable acidity (TTA), and lactic acid bacteria (LAB) development—indicated for all of the experimental trials that the kinetics is comparable to those of the controls. The fermentation quotient of the FHS trial was particularly higher than that of the other trials, including the control production performed with a sourdough inoculum used in an artisanal bakery. The dominance of the added strains indicated the clear persistence of *L. sanfranciscensis* PON100336, *L. brevis* 200571, and *L. plantarum* PON100148 in the obligate–facultative heterofermentative species (OFHS) trial. The pizzas were baked without seasoning in order to investigate weight loss, color, morphology, and a generation of volatile organic compounds (VOCs). The data showed the differences among trials regarding the inocula. Eight classes of VOCs were detected in the pizza samples with aldehydes, esters, alcohols, and acids as major compounds. The sensory attributes were significantly different for the judges and the pizzas. The multivariate statistical approach found marked differences among the trials. The results indicated that the application of mixed cultures of the facultative heterofermentative species of *Lactobacillus* determined high quality pizzas.

The authors would like to apologize for any inconvenience caused to the readers by these changes.

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Reference

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